

HOW TO IMPROVE WRITING SKILL

Ergashova Shahrizoda Elbek kizi

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

Philology and teaching foreign languages

3rd-year student shahrizam406@gmail.com

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Annotation: This article analyzes the significance of composing abilities. Composing aptitudes is an critical angle of scholastic accomplishment. To realize higher levels, you wish constant work on yourself, perusing books, magazines and logical articles. This will hypothetically be accomplished through ponder hone.

Key words: Dictations, improve, read , language, meaningful texts, writing skill, grammatical structures, speaking ability, rewriting texts.

In the modern world, a significant part of interactions between people takes place on the Internet, and very often in writing. Improving the level of written English is an important task in practical learning.

- try to start paragraphs with a capital sentence. It contains the main point of the entire paragraph. You immediately tell the reader what this part of the text will be about, which allows you to grab his attention. A person does not have to scroll through the text in order to understand the main idea by the middle of a paragraph.

- then the main part should go. After you have announced what you will write about, you need to give more information, expand the topic, for example, include relevant links.

- end the thought in a separate sentence. A thought must have not only a beginning, but also an end. Until you have completed one idea, you cannot move on to another - this will confuse readers. Highlight the end of the thought with a separate sentence.

It sounds easy, but in practice, isolating an idea from each paragraph and even stretching it for two or three is not so easy. As a result, you will understand that a significant part of the text does not need to be written at all, because it does not express any thoughts.

Through the practice of this method, you can learn to write meaningful texts. Another most important stage in creating good texts and in learning a language is an independent search for errors. You can optimize and speed up this process using specialized tools. One of them is the Textly. AI service. The system looks for typos, mistakes in grammar, punctuation, gives advice on improving the writing style. It works like this: the user either goes to the site and copies pastes the text for checking into a special editor, or installs the extension for the browser. In the second case, the tool will check texts on the fly right on the site where they are written.

Writing Skills in English require careful attention and practice, since what is written with a pen cannot be cut down with an ax. Although it can be easier to write a letter than to express your thought orally, as there is time to think, comprehend, "google" the necessary information. Today we will analyze a few tips on how to improve your writing skills. These steps are so simple that it is easy to do them, but easy and NOT to do, and the result will only be for the one who still WILL follow them.

Rewrite. Rewrite texts or dialogues at your level. Just start by rewriting the text you recently read in class. This will help you better absorb new vocabulary, new grammatical structures and

reinforce old ones. This will really improve your spelling and make it easy to remember frequently repeated structures.

Write Dictations. This is where you need the help of your friend, who may also want to improve their writing skills. Ask to be dictated to a text or dialogue that you just rewrote recently or another text that you hear for the first time. In this activity you will be able to practice not only your writing skills, but also your listening skills. Just Write. After you've practiced the previous assignments enough times, it's time to write your own lyrics. Again, you can agree with a friend to write each other sms or emails in English about how your day went or what news you heard today, or what you have prepared today. In this task, you will need to already possess grammatical structures and a certain vocabulary that you acquired by simply rewriting texts. In the initial stages, you can write dialogues, taking as a basis the dialogue that you once simply rewrote. Then you can already create your own "masterpieces" in English. To spare you the agony of searching for topics, the British Council offers practical exercises appropriate to your level to help you improve your writing skills learn.english.teens.britishcouncil.org. Make mistakes. Don't be afraid to make mistakes while writing. Mistakes are a prerequisite for improving your writing skills. I do not know of anyone who could achieve perfection in anything without making mistakes. Another question is how well you do your work on mistakes and analysis of mistakes in order to avoid them in the future. And yet, be prepared for mistakes. Just take them as one of the conditions for improving your writing skills, and when doing analysis of mistakes, try to avoid them again. If you are struggling to improve your reading and writing skills in your home country, there is no better place to improve your writing skills than in an English speaking country. Once again in this tip, you will notice that by reading everything in English and leading your daily life in English, you will improve your writing skills. Learning English will also make you read more English, and having English assignments will ensure regular writing. Also, try taking an English course as it will help you develop effective speaking and writing skills.

Never assume that your writing skills are perfect and capable of accepting constructive criticism and feedback from anyone. What you might overlook may be a clear mistake for the native. Therefore, whenever you write, be open to the people who correct you. If someone doesn't understand what you are saying, there are two ways to show you. First, they don't respond properly, and second (more obviously), they ask you what you are trying to say. If you find that people constantly misunderstand you, then you need to keep improving your skills. Apps like Grammarly can help you dramatically improve your writing style. This may not be the solution for you if you are just starting out, but once you have mastered the basics of the English language, you should try Grammarly. This app (and website) corrects your grammar and spelling mistakes and offers you an alternative.

If you don't want to install the app, a simple dictionary and thesaurus will do. It may not help you learn new words, but once you hear or read a word, you can look up it in a thesaurus or dictionary to understand what it means. The thesaurus will show you synonyms (words with a similar meaning), and the dictionary will show you the definition of the word. Both are important when you want to learn how to write in English.

It may sound strange, but many international students think in their own language and then translate their language into English. It's not perfect. Foreign languages and English rarely use

a similar sentence structure. If you want to improve your skills, think in English. By thinking in language, you will find that your writing is more natural rather than forced. And while you think, you will also know where you need to improve your skills. If you keep forgetting words or phrases, this is what you need to practice. Remember, practice makes perfect. You will notice that thinking in English improves your writing and your speaking ability also improves.

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